

Prevalence of Allergic Disorders among the First Year Professional Course Students and to Study the Correlation between Stress and Allergic Disorder

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Abstract:

Background: Prevalence of Allergic disorders is increasing accompanied by rising stress levels in the children which highlights the concerns to study the association between both these factors. The current study was conducted to evaluate the association between stress and allergic disorders.

Materials and Methods: 358 students were enrolled for the study purpose. Perceived stress questionnaire and allergic questionnaire was used to collect the data. All the volunteer students were above 18 years admitted in the year 2021 and 2022 were included in the study.

Results: In our study population of 358 students prevalence of allergic disorder is 45.81%.

In students with allergic disorders 62.91% has perceived stress score [PSQ Score] more than 0.5. Also 72% students with allergic disorders have positive family history of allergic disorders. The association between allergic disorders and stress is significant at p value less than 0.05 according to the chi square statistics.

Conclusions: The psychological factors have a significant role in the exaggeration of the allergic disorders. Stress can exacerbate the allergic disorders so children with positive family history for allergic disorders or those who are more susceptible to allergic disorders are more vulnerable to experience stress triggered allergic disorders hence stress management is important in these children to minimize allergic episodes and prevent future complications in them.

Keywords: Allergic Disorders, Stress, Perceived Stress Score, Students.

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Introduction

Allergies can affect any part of the body, although they most frequently affect the nose, sinuses, respiratory system, skin, and gastrointestinal tract. [1] According to contemporary estimates, there are 300 million people with asthma and 200–250 million people with food allergies worldwide at any given moment. [1]

Allergic reaction occurs due to hypersensitization of immune system by an Allergen. Another element that is really common is the stress that children are dealing with.

The World Health Organization defines stress as any shift that results in physical, emotional, or psychological strain. [2]

Stress can show itself as anxiety, fear, difficulty relaxing, elevated heart rate, trouble breathing, and irregular sleep patterns, change in eating patterns, difficulty in concentrating and worsening of preexisting physical and mental health conditions.

[2] This study is inspired from the Field Of Psychoneuroimmunology, which keeps describing the connections between immune responses, neuroendocrine processes, behavior, and health. [3] Modulation of allergic responses by mood and psychological stressor is also supported by various studies.

1. A study carried out by department of medicine in University of New Castle Australia. In this study the females were divided into allergic and non-allergic group based on the self-reported allergy status and results of the skin prick test.

Result shows poor psychological function in women with Perennial allergic rhinitis. [4]

2. Another study done by NWJ Wainwright in UK (May 2007) this study is a cohort type of study in which data collected from 686 asthma hospitals. The results could be interpreted as psychosocial factors such as current mood problems and

unfavorable childhood situations, negative perceived support were associated with increased rate of asthma hospital admissions independent of other factors like age, sex, obesity etc. [5]

Hence the association between stress and allergic disorders needs to be explored so that we can find an appropriate approach towards allergic diseases.

Aims and Objectives

Primary Objective

- Estimate the prevalence of allergic disorders among first year professional students admitted in 2022-2023
- To find the association of stress in the initiation and exaggeration of the symptoms of allergic disorders.

Methodology

Type Of Study	Descriptive Type
Study Design	Cross- sectional[Questionnaire based]
Study Participants	All the students of first year professional course admitted in session 2021-2022
Sampling Technique	Convenience Sampling
Duration Of Study	After getting ethical clearance from APRIL 2023 TO SEPTEMBER2023
Sample Size	330 [accord. To Danial sample size formula]
Selection Criteria	
Inclusion Criteria	All the volunteer students above 18 years admitted in year 2021-2022 who have given consent
Exclusion Criteria	All those having chronic illness [like DM, HTN, CKD] except allergic disorders.

Data Collection Procedure

Figure 1: Data Collection Procedure

Statistical Tools

Calculating Perceived Stress Score Index: The scores were calculated from the allergic questionnaire according to the response as:

Table 1:

Almost	SCORE :-1
Sometimes	SCORE:- 2
Often	SCORE :-3

The scores for the Question no. 1,7,10,13 17,21,25,29 were reversed as 4=3; 3=2; 2=3; 1=4. Than the total points is summed up and labeled as RAW SCORE. The score for the PSQ INDEX were obtained between 0 -1.

$$\text{PSQ INDEX} = \frac{\text{RAW SCORE} - 30}{90}$$

The calculated PSQ SCORE and data collected from Allergic Questionnaire form was plotted in the form of table on the Microsoft excel sheet.

Results and Discussion

Out of 358 students prevalence of allergic disorder is 45.81%.

62% students with allergic disorders has perceived stress score [PSQ] more than 0.5. Also 72% students with allergic disorders have positive family history of allergic disorders. The association between allergic disorders and stress is significant at p value less than 0.05 according to the chi square statistics.

Figure 2: Value of PSQ in those with allergic disorders

62% students with allergic disorders has perceived stress score [PSQ] more than 0.5. Based on the symptoms of allergic disorders following conclusions have been observed.

- General symptoms include most common weight loss, followed by fever as shown below.

Figure 3: General Symptoms

Respiratory system most common symptom include cough, than shortness of breath followed by wheezing and chest tightness.

Figure 4: Respiratory System

Figure 5:

Gastrointestinal System: Most common symptom in allergic disorders involving git system includes pain abdomen, followed by constipation nausea, heartburn diarrhoea and vomiting.

Figure 6:

Eye, Ear, Nose, Throat, And Lymph Nodes [Among this most common symptom include headache, followed by itchy eyes and sneezing]

Significance of Stress and Allergic Disorders

Table 2: Chi –Square Test [Using Microsoft Excel]

	Allergic Disorder Present	Allergic Disorder Absent	
PSQ > 0.5	102	80	182
PSQ < 0.5	62	114	176
	164	194	364

The P value is calculated after entering the data in Microsoft Excel, the p- value is less than 0.001, which is Significant as p < 0.05.

Conclusion

The psychological factors has a significant role in the exaggeration of the allergic disorders. Stress can exacerbate the allergic disorders so children with positive family history for allergic disorders or those who are more susceptible to allergic disorders are more vulnerable to experience stress triggered allergic disorders hence stress management is important in these children to minimize allergic episodes and prevent future complications in them. These children are advised to practice:

- Meditation or yoga
- Regular exercise [emphasis on breathing exercises]
- Adequate sleep approx. 8 hours
- Engaging in hobbies or extra – curricular activities which give them joy and relax their mind.

Positive family support and supporting friend circle is very important in these children. Also do seek help of medical health professional whenever child experience persistent feeling of sadness, helplessness and hopelessness. Also when child has loss of interest in activities, change in sleep and

appetite patterns, persistent headache, suicidal thoughts do consult the medical health professional.

Early psychotherapeutic intervention can prevent the future complications in these children.

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